

Governing Science through Evaluation: A Global Heuristic of Research Evaluation Regimes

Abstract

The article presents a theoretical reflection on research evaluation regimes – state-initiated historically installed in European countries to coordinate the distribution of research funding – and proposes four dimensions enabling their comparison from a global perspective and potentially advancing future research. We take Michael Power’s argument that evaluations are cultural artefacts and essentially linked to modes of governing as a starting point to further the analytical reflection on the modes of governing science through research evaluation regimes and develop a critical heuristic that accounts for so far neglected aspects

Much of the existing scholarship on research evaluation systems adopts a case-based approach shaped by methodological nationalism, thereby neglecting transnational processes, historical and socio-political variation, and the diverse constellations of and formal and informal relationships between evaluating and evaluated actors. . Based on this critique, we develop a heuristic of four dimensions of research evaluation regimes which can inform future research transnational dynamics and normative aspects. The article identifies the constellation of actors (1), procedures (2), functions (3), and programmes and values (4) as core dimensions of research evaluation regimes which can advance inquiries into the governing of science through research evaluation from a transnational perspective. The heuristic is presented as a starting point to conduct context-sensitive, comparative studies of research evaluation regimes and their governing of science.

Keywords: research evaluation systems, national innovation systems, evaluation studies, governance of science, bibliometrics, metrics

1. Introduction

Scholarly research for a large part is funded by national governments and the allocation of funding is often contested given scarce resources. Against this background, in the early 1970s, many countries, particularly in Europe, established “large-scale systems for evaluating government-funded research at the national level” to address “demands for greater accountability and efficiency, serious funding constraints, and the pursuit of quality improvements” (Coryn et al. 2007, 438). Thus having emerged within a context of competitive funding allocation, these research evaluation systems (RES) represent a complex and dynamic constellation at the intersection of political and scientific logics, often structured in terms of funding sources around the nation state. These systems differ across geographical contexts.

The institutionalised evaluation of science in RES subsequently plays a central role for science systems’ material basis. While evaluation procedures have historically been essential to the self-governing and quality assurance of science, paradigmatically expressed in the institution of peer review (Reinhart and Schendzielorz 2024)¹, the role of RES for steering science through funding allocation by state actors particularly calls for a theoretical reflection on the role of governing modes inherent in RES. By characterising RES as “a variety of responses to incentives and impulses created in the dynamic interplay of politics, management, administration, market forces, media, and research itself” (Hallonsten 2022, 409), previous research has already highlighted RES’ political nature (Hallonsten 2022), presenting the starting point of this article.

¹ In focussing on research evaluation regimes, we are deliberately excluding other evaluation processes in science such as prizes or academic promotions.

Drawing on critical contributions on theories of evaluation, we develop a theoretically-informed perspective on RES as regimes and especially pay attention to the variations in the modes of governing from a global perspective. While many RES are structured in terms of national funding and evaluation agencies, we are additionally considering heterogenous actor-constellations, informal practices and transnational dynamics, such as the reliance on (commercial) research information systems, narratives around what counts as ‘excellent’ research or regional actors. In developing a heuristic of four dimensions of RES, we are decisively not introducing a new classification but a theoretical reflection on these typologies which highlights aspects and dynamics of RES that can advance further comparative work on RES from a global perspective.

Until now, research evaluation regimes have been thoroughly studied either through in-depth case studies or from a comparative perspective, often focussing on their practical workings in terms of methods and tools such as the use of metrics or peer-review or their functions as being summative in distributing funding or formative in enhancing research conditions. In doing so, the nation state often serves as the main frame of reference and distinctly centralised regimes in terms of one central evaluative body such as the British Research Excellence Framework are overrepresented. Existing research has criticised the dominant perspective for its neglect of transnational aspects of research evaluation regimes with global inequalities being the most glaring among them. Similar issues are present in the related and somewhat older literature on national innovation systems (Edquist 2013) which engages with undue nationalism and neglect of informal aspects of research evaluations (see e.g. Freeman 1995; Godin 2009)².

In light of repeated arguments for a globalisation of the sociology of science, we identify abstract features of research evaluation regimes, accounting for different historical and political contexts. By that means, we are less centring on the detailed workings of each regime – as in the existing literature – but instead start from a more broader perspective on underlying narratives and political programmes that shape these regimes.

To do so, we draw on Michael Power’s argument that evaluations are embedded in normative frameworks, cultivating ideas and values, accordingly and are linked to certain related modes of governing. In his seminal work “The Audit Society: Rituals of Verification”, Power proposes to conceive evaluations not only as a technical procedure but as embedded in socio-political contexts and entangled with political functions and normative imaginaries. Studying audits in the British financial sector in context of the explosion of audit practices in the UK in the 1990s, he links evaluations and audits to broader social structures and, by connecting them to programmes of control, forefronts their political and normative aspects.

“[C]hecking up on each other is not simply a matter of technical expediency. It is also a cultural issue, a product of the communities in which we live and the forms of accountability, approval, and blame that constitute our normative environment“ (Power 1997, 2).

Directing the attention towards the underlying socio-political and cultural aspects of evaluations resonates with Dahler-Larsen’s work on the “Evaluation Society” which also emphasises that “[t]he evaluation wave has to do with mentality and culture in many areas of our daily lives“ (Dahler-Larsen 2012, 3). While Dahler-Larsen centres on the idea of measurement as a core aspect of evaluations, Power stresses the measurements’ underlying values of control and considers the wider context of modes of governing.

² Due to the theoretical preference for an evolutionary approach and the integration into the literature in organisation studies (see e.g. the debate around institutional logics: Lounsbury et al. 2021), discussing the literatures on innovation systems alongside with research evaluation systems would require a more extensive format.

From a Foucauldian perspective on power relations, Power stresses that „[a]udit has become a benchmark for securing the legitimacy of organizational action” in that audits are not only functioning for improvements or control but rather communicate and “make these improvements externally verifiable via acts of certification” (Power 1997, 10f.). He thereby hints at the multitude of functions that audits perform besides steering. Audit “is not simply a solution to a technical problem” – e.g. distributing research funding in the context of science – “it also makes possible ways of redesigning the practice of government“ (Power 1997, 10f.). In terms of these practices of government, Power particularly emphasises the different positions of evaluating and evaluated actors in terms of power relations in asserting that audits require trust in auditors and are not “a basis for rational public deliberation. [They are] a dead end in the chain of accountability“ (Power 1997, 127). Subsequently, from his perspective, audits are not linked to a participatory or democratic logic – meaning that different actors and observers of audits are equally involved in decision-makings – but rather that evaluated bodies are asymmetrically assessed³.

Building on Power, we are centrally focussing on these underlying normative and political aspects of RES and present a theoretical reflection on the comparative study of RES. We will first review existing literature on typologies of research evaluation regimes as well as established critiques of its shortcomings in terms of the informal, political, and normative dimensions of research evaluation regimes. In a second step, we develop a heuristic based on four dimensions of (1) the constellation of actors, (2) procedures, (3) functions and (4) programmes and values of research evaluation regimes. This heuristic systematically accounts for the diversity of different research evaluation regimes and their transnational, normative and performative aspects and enlarges the view on RES beyond a focus on state actors or as a top-down steering system. Through drawing on Power’s insights on evaluation as a cultural artefact, we are theoretically reflecting on existing classifications without introducing a new typology or classification such as (Rushforth et al. 2025).

2. The operative working of Research Evaluation Systems: existing Literature

Existing research often starts from a detailed look at the intricate workings of single research evaluation systems and taxonomies comparing different systems critically build on this rich literature. Given the central role of national governments for funding and evaluating research, these works often use the nation state as a central point of reference and frequently draw on particularly centralised systems such as the British REF – which acts as a main body of research evaluation in the UK and can be described as a ‘model case’ (Krause 2021) in that it operates as a dominant case study from which paradigmatic assumptions are developed. However, when approached from a global perspective, the level of centralisation – orientation towards a single evaluative body – and the nation-state focus in the UK represents an atypical case when compared to regional or (post-)imperial research evaluation regimes such as in Latin America or the Soviet Union. Furthermore, existing works predominantly focus on the operative elements of RES (methods, tools employed etc.) while informal and discursive aspects such as the role of the notion of ‘excellence’ remain neglected. In the following, we review existing contributions on comparisons of research evaluation systems as well as existing critiques of the neglect of transnational and informal aspects.

³ Power notably distinguishes audit and evaluation from each other in his final analytical chapter (“audit is a normative check whereas evaluation provides empirical knowledge and addresses cause and effect issues“ (Power 1997, 118), however treats both as similar phenomenon (and presents research evaluations as a case of audits (Power 1997, 100)). Based on this and others who have argued to view „evaluation as an umbrella category covering a range of activities with varying forms” (Dahler-Larsen 2012, 12; Kulczycki 2023, 66), we will not follow Power’s analytical distinction and conceive the boundary as indistinct.

2.1. Taxonomies of Research Evaluation Systems

Established taxonomies of contemporary RES recurrently employ the following distinctions: Ochsner et al. highlight the diversity of research evaluation systems and differentiate between “the stage of evaluation (ex-ante vs ex-post evaluation), link to funding (summative vs formative evaluation), and method of evaluation (metric vs peer review and different levels of evaluation)” (Ochsner et al. 2021, 101). They identify “seven different types of evaluation procedures: accreditation, formative national evaluation, performance-based national evaluation, excellence initiatives, national career promotion, government project funding and evaluation of academies of sciences or research institutes“ (Ochsner et al. 2021, 103). Similarly, in comparing “methods of evaluation used across twelve countries in Europe and the Asia-Pacific region”, Geuna and Martin outline that „in practice, ‘evaluation’ can be divided into *ex ante* and *ex post* forms, and can perform either a summative or formative function” (Geuna and Martin 2003, 278). In a similar direction, for Gläser et al., „the most important distinction is that between RES based on peer review and indicator-based RES“ (Gläser et al. 2010, 153) and they distinguish five dimensions of the informational yield of research evaluation systems (Gläser et al. 2010, 155).

While these contributions focus on the operative and technical aspects of research evaluation systems – the methods, stage and link to funding –, other works additionally consider the temporality and the constellation of evaluating and evaluated actors . Focussing mainly on OECD countries, Whitley argues that evaluation systems “differ in how they are organised and governed, and in their implications for resource allocation decisions. [...]. [W]e can distinguish between evaluation systems in terms of their frequency, formalisation, standardisation and transparency” (Whitley 2007, 6). He identifies the shift of “support for basic research away from block grants to universities to research councils and specialised funding agencies more amenable to state guidance“ (Whitley 2007, 5) as shaping historical development in the 1990s. Importantly, this historical frame of reference has to be contextualised: Whitley’s observation might hold for many Western European and North American countries, however less so for postcolonial or post-soviet contexts as i.a. shown by (Kulczycki 2023) and elaborated in detail in the following section. Whitley distinguishes “two ideal types of weak and strong evaluation systems”, the former referring to constellations of informally organised “funding agencies and/or a consortia of universities with little standardisation of procedures or criteria“ (Whitley 2007, 9), while strong evaluation systems “institutionalise public assessments of the quality of the research conducted in individual departments and universities by scientific elites on a regular basis according to highly formalised rules and procedures“ (Whitley 2007, 9). Upon theoretical reflection, this presumed link of the degree of formalisation of procedures and actors however appears misconstrued: multiple evaluating actors might employ highly formalised processes, notwithstanding, in their heterogeneity do not constitute a centralised system. In fact, more formalisation without effective centralisation seems like a significant effect of evaluative cultures in the last 20 years which is emphasised by Coryn et. al.. While Coryn et. al resonate with Whitley in distinguishing national research evaluation models into “two dimensions: first, as they relate to allocating or distributing research funding, and second, on the basis of their general research evaluation approach or strategy” (Coryn et al. 2007, 440), in addition to either systematic and consistent approaches, they also identify “pluralized approaches that can be characterized by a high degree of situation-specific variability in terms of their conceptions, methods, and applications” (Coryn et al. 2007, 442f.) and thereby complicate the notion of either strong or weak RES. Importantly, they highlight how the level of centralisation or mixed systems of funding are disregarded in literature on RES (Coryn et al. 2007, 442), pointing towards the challenge of characterising systems as (de-)centralised or uniform in terms of actors and processes. This is exemplified by the disregard of the established literature of the US which represents a mixed system consisting of a heterogeneity of actors, funders and mechanisms. The US is described as a poor case to study research evaluation since “[i]ts public universities

compete in the same space with elite private universities, liberal arts colleges, research-intensive institutions, and other peculiar organizational forms [...]. Further, U.S. scholars' work is funded not primarily by the state but by a constellation of organizations, government bodies, corporations, and so on" (Pardo-Guerra 2022, 64). While contributions have studied single institutional actors in the US-System – such as e.g. Lamont in her ethnographic study of peer-review panels in a large funding organisation (Lamont 2009) – a macro-perspective on the interacting state and private funding initiatives and their funding and evaluation practices remains missing. Bringing the existing typologies together, Hicks distinguishes "[p]erformance-based research funding systems according to their unit of analysis, methods of measurement, frequency and census period. Individuals, research groups, departments and universities are all possible targets for evaluation" (Hicks 2012, 254; see also Rushforth et al. 2025). Still, she does not present a systematic heuristic or an account of the interrelation of these aspects.

Overall, these contributions are predominantly focused on the mechanisms of RES and their role in distributing government funding. We will show in the following section that apart from the neglect of mixed systems and non-state actors, also transnational dynamics and informal aspects of RES are often overlooked.

2.2. Beyond methodological Nationalism: Transnational research evaluation

Multiple contributions have already outlined that the studies these taxonomies build on "only cover a restricted amount of countries, usually those for which information is publicly available in English, [...] they do not reflect whether such systems allow for adaptations of evaluation methods on the discipline level [...] [and] they often focus mostly on financial impacts of the evaluation or focus exclusively on performance-based funding systems" (Ochsner et al. 2018, 1235). Oftentimes, starting from the Research Assessment Exercise in the UK (installed in 1986) as a model of national research evaluation systems in introducing a performance-based research funding system (Hicks 2012, 251), the taxonomies neglect alternative transnational and imperial histories of research evaluation.

This established neglect in the literature can be identified as an underlying methodological nationalism – "the assumption that the nation/ state/ society is the natural social and political form of the modern world" (Wimmer and Glick-Schiller 2003, 302): contributions predominantly conduct case studies in nation states, paying little attention to regional or imperial constellations and their impact on the policies and practices of evaluations (Hicks 2012, 251). Apart from overlooking heterogenous non-centralised systems such as the US, existing works on RES do not systematically include regionally oriented evaluation systems such as Latin America where career paths, evaluation procedures, infrastructures such as publication databases are fundamentally shaped by regional institutions (Beigel 2014; Vessuri et al. 2013). The outstanding importance of transnational dynamics can also be found in contributions on the (post-)Soviet space which present an alternative genealogy of research evaluation regimes in the Russian Empire and the Soviet Union and display the legacies of imperial and regional histories onto contemporary research evaluations (Kulczycki 2023, 70ff.; Aronova 2021). These works additionally emphasise, how different political agendas interact with supposedly similar evaluative procedures, e.g. how the use of metrics in, both, British and Russian research evaluations is linked to remarkably different underlying cultural narratives and related political functions (Sokolov 2021).

Apart from highlighting the transnationality of RES and the importance of considering RES in their socio-political contexts, these works on the Global South and East have accused the existing European-focussed literature on RES for its uncritical treatment of exclusionary technical tools (developed by Northern institutions), leading to an ignorance of global inequalities. They fundamentally question the assumed sovereignty of (national) research evaluation research regimes and the interrelation with Northern-based data infrastructures and

indicators of research evaluation (Beigel 2014; Vessuri et al. 2013), its imperial origins (Cramer 2022; Csiszar 2023) as well as the role of language in research evaluation (Curry and Lillis 2004; Smirnova et al. 2021). Being situated in formerly colonised contexts and studying RES in their transnationality, these works also point towards broader global asymmetries which contextualise research evaluation and call for a systematic account of the normative and political dimension of research evaluation regimes. This represents the first starting point for our theoretical reflection and is linked to our second point on the neglect of informal practices in dominant literature on RES.

2.3. Extending the policy-focus on research evaluation regimes: The importance of informal practices

In addition to overlooking transnational dynamics and understudied contexts, existing classifications of research evaluation systems are further challenged by work highlighting how evaluation regimes interact with scholars, their research and career-making practices, and the informal dimensions of evaluation policies. These, in turn, highlight potential workarounds and resistance against evaluative control procedures, the importance of the heterogeneity of actors, as well as transnational disciplinary cultures. Contributions from this perspective stress that while evaluation systems may appear as top-down governing systems from a policy perspective, the ways in which they are performed and dealt with in practice, however, differ widely. They additionally emphasise that scholars are not only evaluated but simultaneously also evaluate, (Reinhart 2023) weakening binary classifications of evaluating and evaluated actors (Schneider et al. 2021).

To begin with, research on practices of evaluation, such as collective decision-making in funding panels or hiring committees (Brunet and Müller 2023; Hamann 2019; Lamont 2009; Reinhart 2012; Roumbanis 2017), shows the diverse informal elements in peer-review evaluation processes in which formalised policies are interpreted and enacted. Secondly, works that look into the effects of research evaluations on scholars' work and research practices or research communities highlight the unintended and negative effects of research evaluation systems and the creative responses of evaluated parties. For the departmental level, Pardo-Guerra shows how the British research evaluation system “perturbated local labor markets for academics, changing the structure of careers in a way that produced more homogeneous institutions [...] [and] changed the way academics made sense of their own worth,” (Pardo-Guerra 2022, 4f.), cautioning to account for the manifold organisational and social practices in which research evaluations are enacted and change the entity of evaluated parties (see also on how rankings create anxiety (Espeland and Sauder 2016). Additionally, more micro-level focussed studies on the effects of research evaluations on individual scholarly practices emphasise disciplinary specificities regarding conflicts between “disciplinary norms (epistemic factors) and general (non-epistemic factors) from funding agencies and evaluation models” (Hammarfelt and De Rijcke 2015, 8). On top of studies examining epistemic effects (Gläser 2024) and researchers' self-understandings (Davies and Bansel 2010; Loveday 2018), further research highlights how evaluation regimes contribute to increased time pressure (Müller 2014) negatively impact researchers' mental health due to heightened stress (Kulikowski et al. 2023; Reinhart 2022), and encourage scholars to ‘game the metrics’ (Biagioli and Lippman 2020; Kulczycki 2023; Macdonald 2022; Robinson-Garcia et al. 2023).

This literature tends to approach evaluation regimes from the perspective of evaluated researchers and highlights the interactive character of research evaluation regimes and researchers' practices. From this view, research evaluation regimes appear not so much as a more or less coherent or centralised governance system and instead as a professional environment of which scholars and organisations are an active part of. This literature can be characterised by a focus on the informal side of evaluation processes, which stands in contrast

to the reviewed taxonomies of research evaluation systems that analyse the formal side of technical and operative aspects. In organizational sociology, the distinction of formality and informality is drawn according to the inclusion of formal roles in member roles – e.g. (standardized) guidelines or rules – and informal roles which are not linked to membership and mostly undocumented (Luhmann 1972). The missing dialogue emphasises the absent conceptualisation of the relationship between the formal and informal processes and practices of research evaluations.

By highlighting negative effects of research evaluations, many of these works possess a critical impetus and emphasise that research evaluation regimes are political. They criticise metrics and their effects, often as part of a more general criticism of neoliberalism, however such criticism tends to simplify the different actor-constellations, socio-political contexts and underlying normative imaginaries of research evaluation regimes.

3. Towards a Heuristic: Dimensions of Research Evaluation Regimes

Theoretically reflecting on the literature on RES against the background of Power's argument for the genuinely political nature of evaluations, led us to develop a heuristic of RES. Conceiving RES as a cultural artefact linked to normative ideals, through this heuristic, we aim to apprehend the identified shortcomings of the existing literature by deemphasizing centralization through national settings and formalization through well-defined procedures and enable further comparative research on RES. By outlining four dimensions of research evaluation regimes, our systematisation captures the (potentially heterarchical) constellation of evaluating actors, associated power structures, governing modes, and underlying cultural narratives that shape these regimes from a global perspective.

The first dimension focusses on the constellation of evaluated and evaluating actors: we assume that evaluation constellations are inherently heterarchical, as both national and disciplinary differences form a dynamic blend, while hierarchical constellations of one core evaluating body (e.g. national state ministry) are exceptions that need to be continuously stabilised. These actor constellations fundamentally impact the workings and logic of research evaluation regimes and their distribution of power. The second dimension identifies the procedures, tools and indicators employed in research evaluation regimes as important characteristics and adds infrastructures and platforms as further distinct features. The third dimension attends to functions of evaluations for which the allocation of scarce resources is most prevalent in the literature. Drawing on Power, we add legitimation, control and dialogue as additional functions. The fourth dimension focusses on socio-political programmes of research evaluation regimes which regard the relationship of science and society: this dimension particularly emphasises the role of the (transnational) cultural aspects of research evaluation regimes.

3.1 Evaluated and evaluating actors: Hierarchical and heterarchical Constellations

The study of research evaluation regimes needs to firstly address the constellation of evaluated and evaluating actors in the studied context, which can be broadly distinguished into hierarchical and heterarchical settings. Actors of RES have previously been typologised as market actors, regulators, and scrutinisers (Engwall et al. 2022), which implies that actors differ primarily as to how close "to the action" they are. Since we employ a more cultural approach, we see actors as always fully embedded, with their relational positioning being an effect of evaluative cultures. From there, the most basic distinction is between those evaluating and those being evaluated (Schendzielorz and Reinhart 2020). We expect such positioning to be dynamic (e.g. actors switching from evaluating to being evaluated) with a second distinction predicated on the temporal stability and concurrent multiplicity of roles for these actors (e.g. evaluating or being evaluated sequentially or in multiple evaluations concurrently).

On a macro-level, permanent institutions such as universities or non-university research institutes represent the major evaluated bodies of research evaluation regimes. This class of

organisations must be distinguished from more temporary organisations, such as research clusters or graduate schools, which are installed for a certain amount of time. On the meso-level, departments (Pardo-Guerra 2022) or programmes are evaluated bodies in research contexts (Whitley 2007, 8). Additionally, institutions that provide research infrastructures, such as libraries or data centres, might be evaluated. Lastly, on a micro-level, evaluations address individual researchers as academic careers or individual contributions (projects or publications) or as epistemic works. The last dimension interacts with the general career system specific to countries or regions (the hegemonic system being the Anglo-American oriented department system with tenure-track; however, a wide variety of other, mostly nationally oriented research career systems exists) (Musselin 2005; Vasen et al. 2023).

On the side of evaluating actors, these might represent political or private entities, philanthropic and academic bodies. On a macro-level, international and regional political institutions such as the United Nations, the European Union or the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States might act as evaluating actors besides national governments. On a meso-level, state-funded and philanthropic foundations and private-sector companies, might fund and evaluate research and researchers (Whitley 2007, 11) in addition to administrative bodies of universities as well as journals and professional associations. On a micro-level, individual researchers evaluate colleagues and their research both in formal and informal settings. Beyond a generally evaluative, (self)critical stance in everyday academic practice, a decentralized network of journals, publishers and conferences provides the backdrop for a pervasive evaluative culture with a myriad of evaluation and reviewing activities by individual researchers (Reinhart 2023). Since many academics are also members of degree granting institutions for students, their evaluation work in teaching and testing bridges evaluative practices between education and research.

Three important aspects need to be considered regarding the actors – subjects and objects – of research evaluation regimes. Firstly, evaluated and evaluating parties are in an interactive relationship together (Hirschauer 2010): institutions react to evaluative mechanisms such as rankings (Espeland and Sauder 2016), especially temporary organisations, which are to a high degree constituted in and oriented towards the evaluation process, and researchers and scholarly communities or departments engage with evaluations by e.g. “gaming the metrics”. Secondly, in many research evaluation regimes, especially individual scholars are both evaluated and evaluating (and members of evaluated and evaluating bodies), hence, the distinction between subjects and objects of evaluation is fluid. Thirdly and most importantly, the relational constellation of different evaluating and evaluated actors severely impacts the distribution of power, i.e. the degree of centralisation.

To conceptualise this, we can draw on insights from literature in the sociology of valuation, for which “the notion of an actual or potential heterarchy, multidimensionality, or plurality of criteria/grammars of valuation and evaluation“ (Lamont 2012, 207) is salient. Luc Boltanski and Laurent Thévenot have argued for conceiving valuation as processes in a plurality of orders of worth: they plea for “considering the possibility of a limited plurality of principles of equivalence which can be used in order to support criticism and agreements” (Boltanski and Thévenot 1999, 365). Bringing their argument into dialogue with organisational studies, Stark has proclaimed that “instead of enforcing a single principle of evaluation as the only legitimate framework, [...] it is legitimate to articulate alternative conceptions of what is valuable, what is worthy, what counts. Such organizations have heterogeneous criteria of organizational ‘goods.’ To signal that this organizational form is a mode of governance that differs from a hierarchy of command and a conceptual hierarchy of cognitive categories, I refer to it as a *heterarchy*” (Stark 2011, 5).

Applied to research evaluation regimes, we can identify different constellations of evaluated and evaluating actors: heterarchical constellation involves a multitude of actors engaged in

various orders of worth, in contrast to regimes governed by a centralised evaluating body. The hierarchical and heterarchical constellations can be further distinguished across multiple levels. For instance, on the meso-level – within universities – scholars may be evaluated according to different logics for promotions, while simultaneously experiencing a highly hierarchical structure at the macro-level if degrees are awarded by a single central institution.

The constellation of actors in different research evaluation regimes can be illustrated by the cases of Germany and the UK: while the German case can be described as a situation of heterarchy given its abundance of research and higher education institutions, funding bodies (both state and private foundations, different ministries, partly conflicting logics for different career paths) and appointment processes with a high degree of informality, in the UK, the REF represents a core institution characterising a more centralised regime. These constellations are closely tied to the distribution of power. In more hierarchical settings, individual evaluating actors possess more power compared to regimes consisting of a multitude of evaluating actors in which evaluated parties – e.g. scholars or departments – are not dependent on a single actor. Research funding organisations, for example, might yield a small amount of power within hierarchical regimes, but in more heterarchical contexts, they can play a significant role by providing essential funding for research institutions, shaping institutional structures and career systems, e.g. in the case of the US.

Altogether, the constellation of evaluating actors and their underlying logic is closely linked to modes of governing research evaluation regimes in terms of centralisation or decentralisation: delineating which entities such as scholars, departments or universities are evaluated by either a single actor or by different funding and evaluation bodies represents a fundamental basis for characterising and comparing different research evaluation regimes. In addition to the constellation of the evaluating actors, research evaluation regimes can be characterised in terms of the procedures, tools (such as indicators) and infrastructures they use for evaluating science.

3.2 Formalised Procedures and Tools of Research Evaluation

The formal procedures and tools of research evaluation regimes – operative and technical – represent the main focus of the existing literature on research evaluation systems: A first distinction can be drawn on a temporal level between regimes that enact *ex-ante* or *ex-post* evaluation procedures as well as *ad-hoc* evaluations, which only take place at certain times. Similar to the constellation of evaluated and evaluating bodies, the frequency of evaluation is linked to different informal functions and power relations within research evaluations: while regular evaluations are often linked to a monitoring or controlling function, *ad-hoc* evaluations are oftentimes more linked to a legitimisation function (Hornbostel 2010, 305).

A second major distinction of formalised procedures of research evaluation regimes can be drawn between metrics- or peer-review-based processes (see above). These procedures are entwined with different logics: while metrics-based systems often create a distance to the evaluated parties through abstracting indicators, the more qualitative peer-review procedures include the scholarly communities and their judgement directly. Consequently, in terms of decision-making logics, metrics-based procedures are leaning more towards an authoritative mode in that they “are created and used to shift the burden of responsibility for the decision that has been taken from those who use metrics to the metrics themselves“ (Kulczycki 2023, 67)⁴. In contrast, peer-review processes are conceived as a more deliberative and interactive process in which the scholarly communities participate and collectively evaluate exerting a high degree of self-control. Existing literature has linked different procedures to actor constellations in claiming that “a unified, state-governed, bureaucratically governed academic sector appears to

⁴ See for the history of the measurement of science and its entanglement with “interest in great men, heredity and eugenics, and the contribution of eminent men to civilization”(Godin 2007, 629) as well as centralisation and metrics-based performance measurement in the historical development of scientometrics (Aronova 2021).

be more inclined to use metrics, while more loosely structured contexts with independent institutions are less prone to introduce indicator-based assessment” (Hammarfelt and Hallonsten 2023, 431). However, one should be careful to straightforwardly link different procedures to specific normative programmes or actor constellations (see 3. 4). A third characteristic of research evaluation regimes on the level of formal procedures is their reliance on or development of tools, indicators and infrastructures, which lead to an active involvement of non- or para-scientific actors. These can be differentiated into those offered by commercial actors, self-administered tools, or Open Access tools and infrastructures. Examples of databases by commercial providers are Clarivate Analytics or Elsevier, Web of Science (WoS) or Scopus for international citation indexes; an example for a tool that is often employed in research evaluations and provided by a commercial actor are the university rankings offered e.g. by Times Higher Education. On the other hand, Scielo represents a large regional open access publication database employed in Latin America or e.g. OpenAlex a global open access bibliometric catalogue. Whoever controls these databases and indicators – e.g. decides about the inclusion of journals, which is especially evident in WoS in which publications in non-English are marginalised – fundamentally influences the research evaluations based on them. As Kulczycki highlights, while some research evaluation regimes build their own databases and involve the scholarly community in doing so, others rely on commercial, Anglo-centric databases and create internal discriminations (e.g. against disciplines that have a strong non-English publishing culture such as in the Social Sciences and Humanities (Kulczycki et al. 2020)).

3.3 Functions of Research Evaluation Regimes

A third dimension of research evaluation regimes relates to their different functions, which the existing literature predominantly discusses in terms of operative procedures being either summative or formative (Geuna and Martin 2003, 278) and related to funding allocation. We propose to also consider the *performative* functions of legitimation, control and dialogue, which have only a loose connection to the allocation of resources (Hesselmann and Schendzielorz 2019; Leckert 2021). In terms of the dominant distinction between the summative and formative function of research evaluation regimes, summative evaluation refers to those procedures that steer the overall higher education and science sector through providing funding linked to national infrastructures of evaluation (e.g. publication databases). In contrast, formative evaluations refer to procedures which are not linked directly to funding decisions and are directed towards the strategic development of evaluated bodies (Hicks 2012). However, this distinction is often fluid given that many formative elements are, in effect, also tied to funding distribution. Apart from funding allocation, on an operative level, research evaluations might also be used to “increase international collaboration; to improve graduate placement“ (Geuna and Martin 2003, 288f.) – hence, steering processes that have historically been in the hands of scholars and students themselves. Moreover, research evaluations are employed to develop policy strategies (ex-ante) (Geuna and Martin 2003, 284; Kropp and Larsen 2023), or in the soviet context, they might function to assess the effectiveness of research plans (Kulczycki 2023, 94f.).

Additionally to their operative functions, research evaluation regimes might also performatively function as legitimising, controlling or enabling dialogue (Molas-Gallart 2012). Firstly, the formalised processes of research evaluations can be used to produce legitimisation through a rationalising of funding decisions: depending on the cultural context of e.g. competition for scarce state resources or accountability towards the public (hence strongly linked to normative ideals (Power 1997, 46)), research evaluations might performatively legitimise public and philanthropic spending. A second performative function of evaluation regimes are forms of social control: in evaluation processes, evaluating parties gain insights into research

organisations and can discipline scholars and research organisations by retracting funding or binding salaries to certain evaluative outcomes. Thirdly, evaluations represent incidences of self-reflection of evaluated bodies (Dahler-Larsen 2012): in anticipation or preparation of evaluations, research institutions initiate communicative and administrative processes that might affect their self-organisation or self-understanding, hence performatively generate evaluating or evaluated actors. This is linked to the creation of – sometimes ritualised – dialogues between different research, bureaucratic, economic and political actors in evaluation processes (Hornbostel 2016, 245), e.g. the common practice for research funders to request bureaucratic reports at the end of research projects that have little to no further value.

These different operative and performative functions of research evaluations are bound to the general social contexts and underlying cultural frameworks in which science and research evaluations are embedded in.

3.4 Programmes and Values of Research Evaluation Regimes: The science-society Link

Historical and contemporary conceptions of science – reflected in cultural narratives – fundamentally affect research evaluation's functions and the values that are enacted in (informal) evaluation practices. Sokolov highlights in his comparison of the use of metrics in research evaluation in the UK and Russia how this operative procedure is linked to very different underlying political programmes in that, “quantification and the usage of metrics in governance can fulfil a variety of different functions and can be seen as offering a solution to different problems” (Sokolov 2021, 990): “in the RAE/REF, the principal role of statistics is to solve ‘the lazy agent’ problem by creating a prisoner’s dilemma for academic institutions, while in the Russian case, statistics serve to solve ‘the corrupt knower’ problem, preventing collusion between the assessor and the assessed“ (Sokolov 2021, 989). Accordingly, a fourth dimension which needs to be reflected on when studying research evaluation regimes are their underlying political programmes or values. As Elzinga and Jamison highlight in their classic account of changing agendas of science policy, “the very idea of science policy is an integral part of a political program on behalf of those in power [...] to use knowledge to achieve their goals” (Elzinga and Jamison 2001, 574). They outline “four main ‘policy’ cultures, coexisting within each society, competing for resources and influence”: a bureaucratic, an academic, an economic and a civic culture which differ in “national styles” and the “degree of centralized authority and regional influence over priorities” (Elzinga and Jamison 2001, 575ff.). Aspects of this dimension are addressed in the literature on the relationship of science and society which has studied the historically changing understandings of science’s role in society in the US (partly also in Europe) and centres on the role of economic structures and conceptions on science. Based on and going beyond this literature, we emphasise to also account for colonial entanglements impacting imperial or colonial political programmes.

Contributions on the history of science-society relations have described the situation, “following World War II, [in] the United States” as a “social contract for science”: “[The] Government promises to fund the basic science that peer reviewers find most worthy of support, and scientists promise that the research will be performed well and honestly and will provide a steady stream of discoveries that can be translated into new products, medicines, or weapons” (Guston and Keniston 1994, 2; Braun 2003; Weingart 1997). In this framework of separated political and scientific spheres and actors with a trustful relationship with each other, the scholarly community to a large degree self-governs itself: Research evaluation was characterised by trust in the scientific communities’ self-organisation and goal-setting. Underlying this conception was “a vision of science as an ‘endless frontier’ that could replace the physical frontier of the American West as a driving force for economic growth, rising standards of living, and social change” (Guston and Keniston 1994, 1), hence a linear model of science development, embedded in a colonialist trope of “expansion”. Godin identifies three stages of development of the concept that “correspond to three policy preoccupations or

priorities: the public support to university research (basic research), the strategic importance of technology for industry (development), and the impact of research on the economy and society (diffusion)” (Godin 2006, 660). This linear and expansionist conception of science development fundamentally influenced the governing of science: instead of trust into the scientific community governing itself, the idea that research has to be applied or needs to have impact presents a significant shift of control: rather than goals identified by the scientific community, it is external aims that are followed and implemented in research evaluation regimes such as through the measurement of “impact”. This increased external control of science by political actors through the setting of overall aims was linked to a framework of internal governance through competition in the EU – or in the words of Elzinga and Jamison a ”technocratic mode of development steered by the new bureaucracies concentrated in Brussels” (Elzinga and Jamison 2001, 595; Elzinga 2012). As shown by research on European science policy, the concepts “excellence and frontier research” travelled from US into European science policy discourses and “have turned into lubricants of competition that buttress an ongoing reform process in Europe” (Flink and Peter 2018, 431). Following Flink and Peter, “both concepts initially conveyed the positive image of individual self-mobilization [and] function as ‘euphemizers’ of competition in Europe” (Flink and Peter 2018, 432). The authors notably relate this idea to the colonialist notion of the frontier which according to them “proliferated an image of an egoistic self-organization in science, based on fierce competition that will cater to the best of society“ (Flink and Peter 2018, 438). They also highlight how „the neoliberal semantics of excellence [...] aim at turning universities and individual researchers into agents of a knowledge-based economic development“ (Flink and Peter 2018, 446).

These contributions emphasise the fundamental role of cultural narratives shaping current research evaluation regimes discursively: the predominant conception of evaluation as a distribution mechanism only is viable in a context in which resources are seen as scarce and scientific communities are externally controlled and oriented towards goals set by political actors and not the scientific community. These works on the historical development of the US and recent European phenomena identify cultural narratives of increased internal competition, external control and a simultaneous decrease in trust: given their focus on the relationship of science with economic development, it is important to emphasise differing political programmes in other contexts. Flink and Peter’s work employs a transnational perspective and spotlights the travelling of concepts and regional conceptualisations of the science-society relationship which becomes even more important in imperial contexts.

Unfortunately, the relationship of science-society relations has yet been only studied on a small-scale in colonial and post-colonial contexts in which research evaluations were entrenched in a colonial/ imperial rule of domination. Singular studies have shown how universities were evaluated and governed to ensure a loyal imperial elite (Pietsch 2013), how databases of publications were shaped by imperial interests (Csiszar 2023), how imperialist agendas shaped Soviet research evaluation (Sokolov 2021), or how colonial science policies in India were related to the enactment and policing of scientific misconduct (Shahare and Roberts 2020). In all these instances, questions of self- and external control of science, underlying notions of competition or trust differ and severely impact research evaluation regimes. These works additionally highlight that the literature on the US and EU research policy with its focus on neoliberal or economic aspects disregards the colonial power relations also entrenched in science-society relations. In order for an adequately global perspective, colonial and capitalist/ neoliberal dynamics have to be both considered in their entanglement.

Against this background, the fourth dimension of comparing research evaluation regimes refers to the broader values and reference points on a national, regional, imperial or global level, such as fostering innovation, international comparability and competitiveness, imperial interests or political goals of regional integration or positioning in foreign politics.

4. Conclusion: Towards a Critique of Research Evaluation Regimes

The article presents a theoretical reflection on RES – state-initiatives historically installed in European countries to coordinate the distribution of research funding – and proposes four dimensions that can advance future research on research evaluation regimes and enable their comparison from a global perspective. We centrally draw on Michael Power’s theory of evaluation who fundamentally understands evaluations as cultural artefacts, linked to modes of governing. Applying his perspective on research evaluation regimes, these are conceived not only as a technical procedures but as embedded in socio-political contexts, being entangled with various functions, normative imaginaries, centrally embedded in underlying narratives of the relationship of science and society. We reviewed the large body of literature on RES which presents detailed insights into the precise workings of research evaluation systems, however can be characterised by an underlying methodological nationalism as well as neglect of different actor-constellations and informal dynamics.

Based on this, we develop a heuristic of research evaluation regimes that accounts for the abundance of different research evaluation regimes beyond centralised examples: the heuristic highlights the importance of the constellation of actors and cultural-normative elements of research evaluation regimes and employs a transnational perspective. Thereby, the governing of science through research evaluation is centrally addressed through the relational study of four dimensions of research evaluation regimes: the constellation of actors (1), procedures (2), functions (3), and programmes and values (4) of research evaluation regimes. In terms of actors, we highlight the fluidity of evaluating and evaluated actors, characterise constellations as more hierarchical or heterarchical, regarding procedures, we caution to consider the underlying infrastructures and their ownership structures, for programmes and values, we highlight that research evaluations might also have performative function of control or function to initiate dialogue and lastly, especially programmes and values are crucially shaped by transnational discourses. Altogether, the heuristic encourages to further transnational studies into different evaluation regimes, their interrelation, and pay particular attention to different modes of their governing (e.g. more authoritarian, deliberative, consensual, competitive or market-oriented). The heuristic shifts the focus of attention towards cultural aspects of evaluation and understands research evaluation regimes as a political playing field of actors as well as entangled with underlying cultural and political narratives and programmes.

Given the large diversity of research evaluation regimes across different contexts and embedded in different – and simultaneously often shared – histories, the heuristic only presents an abstract view on research evaluation regimes and does not address detailed workings of systems. As evident through the references in the texts, the four dimensions we outlined are often overlapping and interacting, hence only can be seen as an analytical observation tool: empirically, many research evaluation regimes might diverge from clear-cut distinctions, however we believe that the heuristic enables a dialogue about different regimes and can be further developed when taking multiple phenomena into account. Especially our emphasis on the transnational dynamics blurs cases: regimes might be closely entangled through shared databases, research information systems or underlying discourses, e.g. about excellence. The challenge of developing an all-encompassing classification is hence addressed through shifting the discussion to a more abstract level instead of building a new classification based on operative characteristics (e.g. peer-review and metrics-based assessments). We strongly believe that given the global character of science and research evaluation (regimes), this comparative view is necessary to account for different modes of the governing of science.

Further research may build on this complication of research evaluation regimes as cultural artefacts and firstly, look into their interrelation with scholars and scholarly communities: if these are not perceived as being “steered” by evaluating bodies and either complying, or suffering from “anxieties” created by rankings or resisting via “gaming the metrics”, the agency and dual role of scholars and scholarly communities as evaluated and evaluating parties is

foregrounded (Schendzielorz and Reinhart 2022). Secondly, this more complex notion of 'steering' emphasises the role of underlying conceptions of the relationship of science and society, trust and control and points towards a more critical view on the politics of research evaluation and global asymmetries. Understanding research evaluation systems as regimes prompts questions of critique, "the art of not being governed like this and at this price" (Foucault 1978), an inquiry long debated in scholarly communities in the Global South around the sovereignty of science.

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